

An Evaluation on the “Municipal Police Officer” Duty of And Organization Metropolitan Municipalities Within the Framework of Norm Staff Principles

Gökhan Karayünlü / Dr.

Mersin University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Department of Political Science and Public Administration

Mersin Police Department Bomb Disposal and Investigation Branch Manager
gokhankarayunlu@hotmail.com

Abstract

Municipalities, established to meet the local needs of densely populated urban areas, are endowed with a range of privileges to adequately fulfill these duties and are tasked with policing the administration to ensure citywide welfare, peace, health, and order. The study examined metropolitan municipalities with larger urban populations than other provinces. Using a qualitative research method, a descriptive study was conducted on the standard staffing requirements of municipalities, the currently employed police personnel, and the activities of police units. The study found that approximately 40% of the total police personnel standard staffing limit is utilized in metropolitan municipalities, and some municipalities publish activity reports specifically for their “Municipality Police Units” and operate effec-

tively and efficiently with their existing staff. In some municipalities, the utilization rate of police officers is extremely low, with this primary duty performed by personnel with a labor status through “direct service procurement,” and the performance of police units in these regions is inadequate. Based on the findings, some recommendations were made regarding the norm staff and employment data and the activities of police personnel.

Keywords: Metropolitan Municipality, Law No. 5393, Law No. 5216, Municipal Police, Law Enforcement.

JEL Codes: H7, H70, H76, H79

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1. Introduction

In the last century, due to factors such as population growth, rural-urban migration, industrialization and agricultural mechanization, cities have continuously expanded in terms of both population and area. This development has necessitated the systematic organization of local administrations in providing common services to citizens. Accordingly, municipalities have created service-specific units to fulfill their duties. Social institutions also change historically according to the lifestyles and needs of societies. The ihtisap institution, unique to Islamic societies, was transformed during the Tanzimat period; the duties of the muhtesip were distributed among the municipal police, military, finance and judiciary, while municipal affairs were transferred to today's municipal police organization (Abay, 2015). Similarly, the municipal police organization, historically influenced by France, assumed duties parallel to current municipal services (Şimşek, 2016).

In larger cities, service-specific institutions have been established, such as İETT, EGO, and ESHOT after the Republic, and the water and sewerage administrations following Law No. 2560 in 1981. While local services were traditionally considered the responsibility of local governments, the new public management approach has redefined them as joint responsibilities of local administrations, civil society and the private sector. Within this framework, Municipality Law No. 5393, prioritizing efficiency and satisfaction, came into force in 2004 (Gürer & Güler, 2015, p. 99).

Today, in increasingly dense metropolitan areas, municipal police are responsible for ensuring public order, health and well-being, implementing municipal council decisions, and enforcing regulations. However, population growth, expanding service areas, political pressures, and limited personnel rights have strained municipal police organizations, which remain under Civil Servants Law No. 657 (Pıçakçioğlu & Ergör, 2005, p. 45)

This study evaluates the "norm cadre" structures, personnel capacities and activities of municipal police departments in metropolitan municipalities through a descriptive analysis of activity reports of 30 metropolitan municipalities and the annual "General Activity Reports of Local Administrations." The lack of previous academic studies on the organizational structure and norm cadre of municipal police reveals both the originality and the limitations of this research.

2. Municipal Police in Literature

With the establishment of the Republic of Türkiye and the subsequent organization of Türkiye's administrative organization, important regulations and changes have been made over time regarding the

performance of public services and law enforcement duties. Municipal police fulfill an important duty in terms of the principle of "subsidiarity" in the performance of local common duties, and it is seen that it is regulated in detail in the Municipality Law No. 1580, which entered into force in 1930. The 104th article of the said law states that "The police are responsible for ensuring and preserving the order, health and boundaries of the town within the municipal borders and in this capacity, they are responsible for the execution of the municipal law, its regulations and prohibitions and the orders given based on them and the penalties imposed in accordance with the law no. 486 dated 16 April 1340 on the provisions of the penal provisions concerning the municipality and its annexes, the performance of the duties set forth in articles fifteen and nineteen and the pursuit and investigation of the crimes by the municipality" and the 108th article states that "Those who oppose the police shall be punished in the same way as those who oppose the state police". On the other hand, under the title of Municipal police Regulation in Article 106, there is a regulation stating that "the profession, qualifications, training and education, promotion and advancement, appointment and dismissal of police officers are determined by a regulation to be prepared by the Ministry of Internal Affairs". As can be seen, in the post-Republican period, police have a key place in municipal legislation and important regulations have been made regarding the nature of the subject with secondary legislation (Law No. 1580). However, there are few studies specific to police in the ongoing period. In the article titled "Municipal police" written by Ertuğ, it is stated that there are no significant study and discussion specific to police force compared to gendarmerie and police organization and that the problems in this regard are not sufficiently expressed. In this respect, it is seen that various suggestions were made in the study in question to protect the order, health and borders of the municipality and to ensure that the authorized police provide more effective service in the execution of municipal regulations and laws and the execution of penalties (Ertuğ, 1947). In his study on the method of use and limitation of the police authorities granted to administrative officers, Günal puts forward the view that the content, method of use and limits of the police authorities should be left to the administrative officer and that only the execution of the issues in question should be granted to the police (Günal, 1959). On the other hand, in an article written in 10966, a case study is given regarding the police authorities granted to administrative officers based on the Council of State Jurisprudence Unification Decision (Günal, 1966). It is seen that the police organization has conducted a study on the effects of smoking and depression on the quality of life of police officers in a narrower scope (Kutlu et al.: 2015). In a study conducted by Şimşek, an ex-

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amination is made on the functional and organizational necessity of the police organization and it is mentioned that there are various functions similar to the duties given to the police within the scope of the current legislation, but there are some deficiencies in various issues such as training and recruitment supporting the organizational structure (Şimşek, 2016). In another study, Usta examines the perception of senior managers in the service sharing of district and metropolitan municipalities by taking Ordu and Trabzon provinces as examples within the scope of the analysis of police service sharing in the metropolitan municipality model (Usta, 2013). In his study, Yıldırım addressed the municipal personnel system in Türkiye and therefore the subject of law enforcement and concluded that the principles of merit and career were not sufficiently functional in the implementation of the personnel system in the Samsun Metropolitan Municipality (Yıldırım, 2019). In his study, Akman and Bayram addressed the difficulties experienced by law enforcement in providing services and performing their duties in the city of Isparta, and the issues that could be improved (Akman & Bayram, 2018). On the other hand, Yüceyilmaz and Özgür, who examined the municipal norm cadre regulations, although not specifically about law enforcement, interpreted the norm cadre regulation and the cadre and annex tables in their study (2018). In fact, it was determined that Yüceyilmaz and Özgür (2018), Peker and Şen (2015) and Alıcı (2017) conducted general research on municipal norm cadre in various municipalities.

In the literature review given above, it is seen that the police organization has not been subject to a study specific to metropolitan municipalities within the existing norm cadre principles and limitations, and especially the activities of the police cadres have not been compared with the metropolitan municipality activity reports. In this respect, considering the fact that no study has been conducted specifically on the “Norm cadre” and “Organization” regarding the police duty carried out in metropolitan municipalities, it is understood that the aforementioned study is original and, as mentioned before, the subject has not been addressed specifically in the literature.

3. Municipal Police in Local Governments

According to the Municipality Law No. 5393, which came into effect in 2005, “police” units are among the units that must be established in municipalities. Again, according to this law, among the duties of mayors; there is a duty that is quite general and attributes responsibility to the mayor as “To take the necessary measures for the peace, well-being, health and happiness of the townspeople”, and mayors fulfill this primary duty through police.

When the “Metropolitan Municipality Law” No. 5216, which entered into force in 2004, is examined,

it is seen that the term “police” is only included in the 7th article, which regulates the duties of metropolitan municipalities, as “To perform police services in areas where the metropolitan municipality is authorized or operates”, and in the 24th article, which regulates the expenses of metropolitan municipalities, as “Expenses to be incurred for the execution of police and fire services and other duties and services”. On the other hand, there are many regulations in the same law regarding the application of Municipality Law No. 5393 in cases not covered by Law No. 5216. When this provision is taken into consideration, it is seen that Law No. 5393 contains fundamental regulations regarding police. Article 51 of Law No. 5393 on Municipalities, titled “Duties and authorities of the police”, reads as follows: “The police are responsible for ensuring the welfare, peace, health and order in the town and for this purpose, they apply the orders and prohibitions taken by the municipal council and to be carried out by the police, and the penalties and other sanctions stipulated in the legislation on those who do not comply with these.” The continuation of the article also states that the sanctions to be applied to those who prevent the police from performing their duties during the performance of their duties are considered identical to those of law enforcement officers.

On the other hand, within the scope of the said article, it has also been regulated that a regulation will be put into effect by the tutelage authorities in order to clarify the working principles, duties, authorities, responsibilities of the police organization, the conditions to be sought for entering the police officer position, examination, in-service training, promotion in accordance with the career principle, dress code, vehicles to be used for defense purposes and other issues regarding the police organization.(Sevgili,2012) Thus, an authority has been granted to the tutelage authorities in this direction in accordance with the principle of “Administrative Law.” Based on this, the “Municipal police Regulation”, which regulates “the establishment, duties, authorities and responsibilities of the police organization, the qualifications of the police officers, their promotion and professional training, their uniforms and working procedures and principles” was published and put into effect in the Official Gazette dated 11.04.2007 and numbered 26490. In the said Regulation, five different arrangements were made on different dates between 2011-2021, and the provisions of the said Regulation are currently implemented by all municipalities.

In the said Regulation, the police are defined as “the special police force that maintains the order of the town, protects the well-being, health and peace of the town’s people, and implements the decisions to be taken by the authorized bodies for this purpose”, and the police are classified as “department head, director, branch manager, chief, commissioner and officer” as an organization.

Within this framework, the police organization is entered as a police officer, and the candidate must first take the Public Personnel Selection Exam. To recruit a police officer, municipalities must first obtain permission from the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change if there is a vacant officer position in the standard cadre. Following this permission, the exam announcement is made and five times as many candidates are invited to the exam, starting from the highest score among the applicants for each vacant position. According to the relevant Regulation, those who will apply for the exam;

- a. Must meet the general conditions specified in Article 48 of Law No. 657,
- b. Must be at least a high school or equivalent school graduate,
- c. Must be at least 1.67 meters tall for men and 1.60 meters tall for women, provided that the weighing and measuring is done on an empty stomach, undressed and barefoot, and there must be no difference of more than (+, -) 10 kilograms between the part of the height that is more than 1 meter and the weight,
- d. Must not have reached the age of 30 on the date of the exam,
- e. Must have received the minimum score specified in the exam announcement from the KPSS score type that has not expired.

Candidates who are successful in the written or oral exam and practical exam to be held on the subjects included in the relevant Regulation are started to work as police officers.

Article 10 of the said Regulation regulates the duties of the police officers and the said duties are regulated in detail under the titles of "Duties related to the order and well-being of the town", "Duties related to construction", "Duties related to environment and health", "Duties related to traffic" and "Duties related to assistance". Article 11 of the Regulation also includes the authorities to be used by the police officers while performing these duties. When the nature of the duties listed under the main headings above is examined, it is understood that they include duties arising from special laws and duties assigned to police by the said regulations.

During the performance of these detailed and comprehensive duties by the police; It is also seen that they are equipped with the authority to conduct inspections on the issues they are responsible for, to request information and documents from the relevant parties, to draw up reports in case of non-conformity to the legislation, to report the situation to the law enforcement authorities in case of negativities and resistances encountered during the performance of their duties, to draw up reports in order to prosecute in this matter, to prevent the sale of prohibited materials in order to establish peace and

security in public places and to report the situation to the relevant authorities, to detect, prioritize and take the necessary legal action against negativities such as noise, environmental pollution and occupation of public areas that negatively affect social life.

3.1. Duties and Authorities of Municipal Police Units

The police departments established in cities with metropolitan municipalities operate under the general secretariat or the relevant deputy general secretary within the metropolitan municipality hierarchy. The department head, as the highest officer of the police organization, conducts the services and duties within their own fields through the branch manager, chief, commissioner and officers who are their subordinates. The department head, who is primarily responsible for all duties and authorities of the police organization, is responsible for his hierarchical superiors in all matters. The general duties, authorities and responsibilities of the Municipal police Department Heads are given below, based on the Working Regulations or Directives of the Municipal police Department Heads of metropolitan municipalities.

- a. Coordinate the work of the units affiliated to the department within the framework of the Strategic Plan and Performance Program,
- b. Prepare the budget of the department in accordance with the performance program and submit it for approval,
- c. Ensure that the work and transactions conducted in the unit are conducted in accordance with the prepared work processes,
- d. As the spending authority, conduct the work and transactions in accordance with the objectives, economic management principles, control regulations and legislation every year and prepare the internal control assurance declaration and add it to the unit activity reports,
- e. Follow up the legislation, innovations and technical developments related to the unit and ensure their implementation,
- f. Ensure that the unit activities are reported periodically,
- g. Ensure that the unit works in cooperation and harmony with the unit and other units while performing its duties,
- h. Ensure the employment of sufficient number and quality of personnel and the distribution of duties of the personnel,
- i. Ensure in-service training of the personnel and their training in accordance with their job qualifications,
- i. Periodically evaluate the performance of its sub-

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- ordinates and conduct activities to increase morale, motivation and performance in the unit,
- k. Take similar measures to be given by the superior to perform other duties of a nature,
 - l. To ensure supervision and coordination in cases were metropolitan municipality police and district municipality police work together,
 - j. The Department Head is authorized and responsible to the upper management in ensuring that the above-mentioned duties are fully and timely performed.

Although the internal norms put into effect by the relevant municipalities regarding the duties, authorities and responsibilities of the Municipal police Department Heads are like each other, it is understood that they regulate the administrative duties of the department head and their hierarchical subordinates. In other words, the Municipal police Regulation has classified the hierarchical chain that will serve in the police units in municipalities as “Department Head, Director, Branch Manager, Chief, Commissioner and Officer”; however, it has not included their duties, authorities and responsibilities. The same Regulation has regulated the duties of the police in detail under five main headings: “Duties related to the order and well-being of the town”, “Duties related to construction”, “Duties related to the environment and health”, “Duties related to traffic” and “Duties related to assistance”. Municipalities, on the other hand, have made their own internal arrangements by using these duties and authorities, considering administrative duties. It is understood that the primary duties of the police are included in a single article as “To fulfill, monitor, supervise and coordinate the duties, authorities and responsibilities of the police in the legislation.” It is understood that the duties listed above are distributed hierarchically from top to bottom among the Police Department Manager, Municipal police Chief, Commissioner and Officer, and the duties of the directorates are determined specifically for duties related to “Order and welfare of the town”, “Development”, “Environment and health”, “Traffic” and “Aid”, and that the police work in coordination with the relevant units within the scope of these duties, just like the distinction between administrative and judicial police. For example, it is evaluated that the police perform a judicial police duty upon detection of illegal construction

in matters related to zoning, that they also undertake administrative police duty in preventing zoning pollution through continuous inspections at the beginning or before the construction of the illegal construction, and that during this period they must work in coordination both within their own unit and with other units.

It is crucial for law enforcement personnel to maintain social and economic peace while serving as auxiliary law enforcement officers. However, the manipulation and manipulation of law enforcement by some elected municipal officials to align with their own political views undermines the impartiality of the police in providing public services. The frequent and frequent changes in municipal administration disrupt the current system and complicate the performance of their duties (Pektaş,2003).

Another important issue is that the privatization of municipal facilities and service houses may lead to the deterioration of uniformity in field practices between the Municipal Police, which are the law enforcement and control mechanism of the municipalities, and the privatized ones in terms of security, cleanliness and service quality (Esen,2021).

3.2. Municipal Police in Metropolitan Municipalities Norm Cadres

In order to regulate “effective and efficient use of public resources, balanced distribution of local services, increasing the quality of services provided by municipalities, employment of personnel with the required qualifications, titles and numbers” in both municipalities and metropolitan municipalities, the “Regulation on the Principles and Standards of Norm Cadres of Municipalities and Affiliated Institutions and Local Administration Unions” was published in the Official Gazette dated 22.02.2007 and numbered 26442 and entered into force. The regulation classifies municipalities according to various parameters, primarily population, and determines the number of personnel based on these classes. According to the Regulation; (A) Group: Metropolitan Municipalities, (B) Group: Provincial Municipalities, (C) Group: Metropolitan District Municipalities, (D) Group: District and Town Municipalities.

In our study, the data for Group (A) (Metropolitan Municipalities) are given below.

Table 1. Metropolitan Municipality Categories According to Population Distribution

Group A Categories	Population Range	Metropolitan Municipalities
A-1	0-999.999	Erzurum, Eskişehir, Malatya, Mardin, Ordu, Trabzon
A-2	1.000.000-1.999.999	Aydın, Balıkesir, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Sakarya, Samsun, Tekirdağ, Van
A-3	2.000.000-2.999.999	Adana, Antalya, Gaziantep, Kocaeli, Konya, Şanlıurfa
A-4	3.000.000-4.999.999	Bursa, İzmir

A-5	5.000.000-7.499.999	Ankara
A-6	7.500.000 Ve Üzeri	İstanbul

Source: Prepared by the author based on the Regulation on Norm Cadre Principles and Standards of Municipalities and Affiliated Organizations and Local Administration Unions.

The above table shows the classification of metropolitan municipalities in category A based on population. The table below shows the upper limit of police cadres to be employed in each category.

Table 2. Upper Limits of Municipal Police Cadres by Category

Cadre	A-1	A-2	A-3	A-4	A-5	A-6
Municipal Municipal Police Department Head	1	1	1	1	1	1
Municipal Municipal Police Branch Manager	5	7	8	10	12	14
Municipal Municipal Police Chief	15	21	24	50	60	140
Municipal Municipal Police Commissioner	45	63	72	150	180	420
Municipal Municipal Police Officer	225	315	360	750	900	2520
Total	291	407	465	961	1153	3095

Source: Prepared by the author based on the Regulation on the Norm Cadre Principles and Standards of Municipalities and their Affiliated Institutions and Local Administration Unions.

According to the table above, the maximum norm cadre data granted to metropolitan municipalities based on population, in a series from the Head of the Police Department to the police officer within the scope of the hierarchy principle, and the current number of police personnel of metropolitan municipalities are included. When this table and the infor-

mation provided previously are taken into consideration, it is understood that a total of 16,404 police personnel cadres have been allocated for 30 metropolitan municipalities. The table below includes metropolitan municipalities that include the number of police personnel in their strategic documents and activity reports.

Table 3. Metropolitan Municipalities Norm Staff Upper Limit and Current Employed Municipal Police Numbers (2023)

City	Population	Km ²	Norm Cadre Upper Limit	Employed Municipal Municipal Police Officer	Percentage Between Norm Cadre and Employment
İstanbul	15.655.924	14.125	3.095	1.417	45,78
Ankara	5.803.482	25.437	1.153	448	38,85
Bursa	3.214.571	10.882	961	203	21,12
Adana	2.270.298	13.844	465	271	58,27
Antalya	2.696.249	20.177	465	94	20,21
Konya	2.320.241	40.838	465	78	16,77
Şanlıurfa	2.213.964	19.242	465	30	6,45
Mersin	1.938.389	16.010	407	205	50,36
Denizli	1.059.082	12.134	407	286	70,27
Hatay	1.544.640	5.524	407	144	35,38
Kahramanmaraş	1.116.618	14.520	407	83	20,39
Erzurum	749.993	25.006	291	66	22,68
Trabzon	824.352	4.628	291	154	52,92
Total	41.407.803	222.367	9.279	3.479	37,49

Source: Prepared by the Author by Examining the Activity and Audit Reports of the Municipalities and Their Websites.

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One of the most important elements of local government is the municipal police, which is responsible for maintaining urban order and ensuring the efficient execution of municipal services. However, the number of employed police officers often falls below the legally established upper limit for standard staffing. The table data shows that this situation poses a serious problem, particularly for metropolitan municipalities.

The total population of the 13 metropolitan municipalities examined in Turkey is around 41.4 million. While the standard upper limit for staffing in these cities is 9,279, the actual number of police officers on duty is only 3,479. Therefore, only 37.5% of the staffing capacity is effectively utilized. Significant differences are noted between the following cities:

- a. Despite a population of 15.6 million in İstanbul, only 45.7% of the standard staffing capacity is occupied. This rate indicates a serious inadequacy at the metropolitan level.
- b. While the rate in Ankara is close to the national average at 38.8%, this level can be considered inadequate considering its status as the capital.
- c. The Şanlıurfa example is quite striking; while the standard staffing capacity is 465, the actual number of employees is only 30. This indicates that capacity utilization is at its lowest level, at 6.45%.

In contrast, capacity utilization is relatively higher in cities such as Denizli (70.3%) and Trabzon (52.9%).

In general, it can be said that municipal police employment is insufficient in cities with high population density and large surface area. For example, in provinces with large geographical areas such as Konya (40,838 km²) and Antalya (20,177 km²), the rates are as low as 16.7% and 20.2%, respectively. This situation complicates the effective supervision of services spread over a wide area. In light of this data, the following observations can be made:

- a) Capacity utilization problem: The difference between the standard staffing and actual employment prevents services from being operated at full capacity in many cities.
- b) Regional disparities: While the rate is relatively high in some Aegean and Black Sea provinces, serious deficiencies exist in Southeastern and Central Anatolian provinces.
- c) Risk to service effectiveness: Low employment rates in cities with large populations and large surface areas negatively impact the effectiveness, accessibility, and oversight capacity of municipal police services.

Consequently, the imbalance between municipal police staffing and employment poses a significant obstacle to the fair and effective delivery of local services. Moving forward, it is crucial to revisit staffing planning to take into account both population

density and geographical reach, and to bring actual employment closer to standard staffing levels.

According to the Unit Activity Report of the İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality IMM Police Department, 430 personnel are employed by direct service procurement. In Bursa Metropolitan Municipality, 620 personnel are employed by direct service procurement. The municipalities' activity reports do not include the details of this information, which is given as a worker status in the police units, and it is not sufficiently understood whether the personnel in question are permanent municipal workers or workers employed by direct service procurement. When this issue is taken into consideration, it is understood that 7 personnel are employed in Ankara, 45 in Antalya, 111 in Konya, 138 in Şanlıurfa, 352 in Mersin, 162 in Kahramanmaraş and 224 in Trabzon. However, it is also debatable to what extent it is healthy for the continuous police duty to be conducted not by police officers but by personnel employed by municipal companies and working as workers, who do not have professional guarantees and assurances. In other words, it is also unknown to what extent municipal company personnel can perform their duties independently and in accordance with the legislation, especially in neighborhoods where local motives and politics are dominant.

On the other hand; because of comparing the population and the number of employed police officers and managerial personnel; there are 11,048 people per police officer in İstanbul; 12,952 people in Ankara. It is seen that the highest population per police officer is in Şanlıurfa with 73,798 people; and the lowest is in Denizli with 3,703 people. Since the surface area, population, settlement characteristics of the city and the activities within the control area of the police differ, it is evaluated and suggested that different studies can be conducted by researchers on each of the mentioned issues.

3.3. Municipal Police in Activity Reports of Metropolitan Municipalities

When the data obtained from the activity reports and other strategic documents published by metropolitan municipalities at certain periods are examined, it is seen that a sizable portion of these units work effectively when the current personnel numbers are considered.

It is also seen that the practice of employing police personnel through municipal companies through direct service procurement is also implemented, some municipalities include this issue in their activity reports and announce the number of personnel employed, but most municipalities do not provide information on this issue, do not prepare activity reports specific to the police and do not disclose this

information to the public within the framework of transparency and accountability principles. In this respect, it is seen beneficial for police to prepare "Municipal police Activity Reports" specific to their own organizations and to inform the public by publishing this information on their websites. It is also clear that this practice will increase the effectiveness and efficiency of police units. Within this framework, it is a general rule that services that are continuous with the changes in question are provided by civil servants, and the public benefit is seen in the employment of personnel in this direction, in other words, in not employing police personnel by directly purchasing services. It has been determined that while there is not enough information specific to police in the activity reports of metropolitan municipalities, limited information is provided in terms of the activities conducted in general. It has been observed that police units in Ankara and İstanbul prepare activity reports within the scope of their own activities, and especially the activity report of the İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality Municipal Police Department is quite comprehensive. It has also been understood in the said report that the police unit determines indicators and performance indicators in line with the strategic goals and objectives of the municipality. In this context, it is seen that they have determined themes under the titles of "Resilient İstanbul", "Accessible İstanbul", "Environmentally Sensitive İstanbul", "Productive İstanbul", "Sharing İstanbul", "Living İstanbul" and the performance of the goals and targets is systematically monitored with indicators specific to development, environment, traffic, urban well-being and other local common services. In the said indicators; It has been understood that the inspection of public transportation vehicles, demolition decisions as a result of zoning inspections, excavation-construction/demolition waste inspections, workplace inspection activities, unsanitary institution and sanitary institution inspections, announcement and billboard inspections, price tag, tariff, tare and shopping mall parking lot inspections, terminal and market inspections, combating begging inspections, inspections to prevent unregistered economic activities (peddlers), licensing activities and inspections, inspections regarding the protection of consumer rights and administrative sanction reports and fines issued based on these inspections were monitored (IMM Municipal police Activity Report, 2023). In the said activity report, it was seen that the 2023 targets were achieved with 100% performance. In Ankara Metropolitan Municipality, although there is no systematic report in this direction, it has been observed that data on inspections in activity areas such as traffic inspections, excavation, zoning pollution, illegal construction, announcements and advertising signs, market hall and terminal, street vendors, beggars, noise pollution, as well as the minutes and fines kept are included in

tables (ABB Municipal police Activity Report, 2024). In İzmir Metropolitan Municipality 2023 Activity Report; Within the scope of the performance goal of "Conducting Municipal police Inspection Activities for Public Health and Well-being and Ensuring the Protection and Security of Service Provided Areas", targets were determined as "Conducting Protection and Security Services", "Conducting Municipal police Services", "Conducting Municipal police Inspection Services", "Conducting Municipal police Traffic Services" and "Conducting Environmental and Zoning Municipal police Services", and it has been observed that the determined targets were achieved within the scope of 2023 (İzmir Metropolitan Municipality Activity Report, 2023).

In other metropolitan municipalities, it was observed that police activities were generally monitored under the following activities: "Environmental Inspections", "Building Control Inspections", "Visual Pollution", "Fighting with Visual Pollution", "Marketplace and Bus Station Inspections", "Inspections and Controls for Consumer Rights". However, it was understood that systematic and performance-evaluating model-reporting was not developed as in the three major cities. In Şanlıurfa, the city with the lowest rate of police officer employment, various activities were included under the headings of workplace, bus station, street vendor, beggar, traffic and consumer rights, and when the number of personnel is taken into account, it is understood that the activities remained limited compared to other metropolitan municipalities (Şanlıurfa Metropolitan Municipality Activity Report, 2023).

In Denizli, where the employment rate of police officers is the highest, the performance of police activities is monitored with three indicators: "Number of advertisement and ad inspections/inspections", "Number of sanitary workplaces inspected" and "Number of non-sanitary workplaces inspected" within the framework of the performance goal of "Performing police services quickly, with high quality and in a fair manner", and it is understood that the performance of the municipality, which employs proportionally more police officers than other metropolitan cities, is not sufficient in this context and is evaluated with limited indicators (Denizli Metropolitan Municipality Activity Report, 2023).

According to the information provided above, it has been observed that police activities in Ankara metropolitan municipalities, especially in İstanbul, are systematically monitored with separate activity reports, their performance is more measurable, and that there is essential information and performance data in this direction in the general activity report of İzmir Metropolitan Municipality. However, no such determination has been made in other metropolitan municipalities, and it has been understood that limited data is shared.

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It was mentioned that the ratio of the employment of police personnel to the standard number of cadres in metropolitan municipalities is quite low and that police personnel are commonly employed through “Direct Service Procurement” in these municipalities. In this respect, it is evaluated that the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change should clarify the issue of employment through direct service procurement specifically for police personnel or should adopt a quota that does not exceed a certain percentage of the standard number of cadres, which would establish a more effective and accountable police unit. On the other hand, it is also considered beneficial to audit police services through performance measures to ensure more accountable and transparent management. It is evaluated that subjecting the police units of municipalities to performance audits by taking the performance indicators applied in İstanbul and Ankara Metropolitan Municipalities as a basis and determining new indicators in the audits of the Ministry of Interior or the Court of Accounts will encourage both the efficiency of the service and the rational use of cadres.

4. Conclusion

To provide local common services, municipalities, which are also called service groups among local government units, need officers and an organization in law enforcement to provide their duties effectively and efficiently. Accordingly, for municipalities to perform their duties of a wide variety of nature throughout the city and accordingly to ensure well-being, health, peace and social order in the city, a “police” unit and personnel must be active. According to the current legislation, the duties, authorities and responsibilities of the police units in municipalities are regulated by the “Municipal police Regulation” and the police units and officers are authorized as a local police force. In metropolitan municipalities, considering both the large population and the size of the service area, the police organization had to be designed accordingly. According to the said legislation, it is mandatory to establish Municipal police Departments in metropolitan municipalities and personnel are employed in these units as “department heads, directors, branch managers, chiefs, commissioners and officers.” In 30 metropolitan municipalities, 16,404 cadres were allocated with standard cadres, and in 13 metropolitan municipalities that included information on police personnel in their strategic documents, 9,279 personnel cadres were allocated with standard cadres, and it was determined that 3,722 of these cadres were used, in other words, an average of 37.49% of the total cadres were used. In some of the municipalities in question, in addition to police officer personnel, police personnel were also employed as workers affiliat-

ed to municipal companies through “direct service procurement”, and when these numbers were taken into consideration, it was understood that there were personnel performing police duties well below the standard cadre limit.

The police officer profession, which is entered through a special competitive exam and requires various conditions to be met, is a cadre that provides the opportunity to advance within a hierarchical chain in accordance with the principles of career and merit. This cadre, which is a local police force in accordance with the current legislation, has duties arising from many special legislations, from urban health and well-being to the environment, from zoning to traffic. Therefore, it is evaluated that if the mentioned cadres are used rationally and the tasks are conducted effectively, local joint services will be provided as required. However, it is seen that in the municipalities whose information can be accessed within the scope of the study, on average 37% of the cadres are used, employment through direct service procurement is also common, in both cases, the total personnel remains well below the standard cadre allocation, and on the other hand, there are drawbacks in the quality and continuity of the service provided by worker personnel who do not have professional security. When the cadre rates are taken into consideration, it is seen that the ratio of civil servant police personnel to the cadre envisaged by the standard cadre is 6.45% in Şanlıurfa, indicating the lowest employment. On the other hand, it is understood that the highest employment rate is in Denizli with a rate of 70.27%. Within the framework of this information, when the 37% average in metropolitan municipalities where police officer data is accessed is taken into consideration, it is seen that the police officer employment rate in metropolitan municipalities varies, the police employment rate decreases as the population increases, and as a result, the police officer cadres determined in accordance with the standard cadre are not used effectively. In the case of Ankara and İstanbul, it has been determined that metropolitan municipalities publish detailed information containing Municipal police Department Activity Reports, that numerical information including performance data on important duties such as zoning, environment, health, license, and traffic is included, and that an effective police service is provided with systematic and measurable indicators in the police units. However, no such information has been found in other municipalities, and no concrete and effective activities have been found to show effective performance in the administrations that employ a small number of people and/or try to provide police services through direct service procurement. In this context, it is evaluated that the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change can clarify employment through direct service procurement for police personnel or implement

a quota that does not exceed a certain percentage of the norm staff number, which will establish more effective and accountable police units. In addition, it would be useful to conduct performance audits by considering the indicators applied in İstanbul and Ankara, which will measure police performance, in the audits of the Ministry of Interior or the Court of Accounts. It is thought that such an audit will ensure rational use of personnel numbers, and that positive changes will occur in the well-being, health and peace of the city, together with more accountable and transparent service delivery. Furthermore, the findings reveal the inadequacy of municipal police employment, particularly in cities with large populations and large land areas. As seen in Konya (40,838 km², 16.7%) and Antalya (20,177 km², 20.2%), the risk of inadequate oversight and effective maintenance of services across large areas arises.

Based on the data obtained from all these studies, the imbalance between municipal police personnel and the standard staff negatively impacts the equitable, accessible, and efficient delivery of local services. Therefore, staff planning should be reevaluated not only based on population data but also on the geographic size and service diversity of cities. Furthermore, bringing actual employment closer to the standard staffing levels is critical for the quality of municipal services and the order of urban life.

Information About Ethics Committee Approval

In this study, all rules specified to be followed within the scope of the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive" were followed. None of the actions specified under the second section of the directive, "Actions Contrary to Scientific Research and Publication Ethics," were conducted.

Research and Publication Ethics Statement

When the study is a Research Article, an ethics committee is not required.

Contribution Rate Statement

Since the entire study was prepared by a single author, the author's contribution rate is 100%.

Conflict of Interest Statement

There is no financial or personal connection with any person or institution in the research. There is no conflict of interest in research.

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An Evaluation on the “Municipal Police Officer” Duty of And Organization Metropolitan Municipalities Within the Framework of Norm Staff Principles

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